

PTC Seed Grant Final Report
July 31, 2019

Impacts of anti-immigrant sentiments on adolescent wellbeing in the Arizona-Sonora border region

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Project Overview: Briefly describe your proposed project and where you are in terms of the development process. Were the proposed activities completed as planned? Please explain how this grant has benefited the research program of your group -if you received a cluster seed grant-, or your personal program -if you received an individual seed grant-.

Our project had three aims:

1. Explore the impact of anti-immigration sentiment, policies, and violence on migrant adolescents in both Nogales, Sonora and Nogales, Arizona, non-migrants in Nogales, Arizona, and recent deportees residing in Nogales, Sonora;
2. Explore the positive and negative coping strategies employed by these adolescents as a result of their experiences with anti-immigrant sentiment, policies, and violence; and
3. Assess how these experiences and coping strategies affects the mental health and wellbeing of adolescents on the Arizona-Sonora border.

Overall, our proposed activities were completed as planned. The activities completed include: recruitment and training of facilitators, recruitment and data collection from 42 adolescents living along the Arizona-Sonora border, and completion of preliminary data analysis. In January 2019, we conducted an in-depth facilitator training for interviewers and transcribers. The purpose of the training was to communicate to the facilitators about the research study goals and methodology and to build a successful team in order to facilitate completion of the grant activities. Between February 28 and May 16, 2019, we recruited participants and conducted 5 focus groups with 24 adolescents and 18 individual interviews. All participants were enrolled in one of eight high schools selected for this study. In Nogales, Sonora, all data collection activities occurred in schools. In Nogales, Arizona, all data collection activities took place in the participants preferred location (school or home). All participants, or their parents in the case of minors, signed informed consent. Individual interviews lasted 30-45 minutes, and focus groups lasted around 2 hours. Data transcription and preliminary data analysis concluded in June, 2019.

This grant greatly benefited our research program. The goal of the Global Center for Applied Health Research is to facilitate collaboration between communities with similar needs and challenges and impact the health of communities in ways that are culturally appropriate, feasible, efficacious,

replicable, and sustainable. The findings learned through this PTC research project have allowed us to explore how coping behaviors are employed by adolescents to contend with anti-immigrant sentiments, policies, and violence, as well as, how these factors contribute to the mental health and well-being of adolescents living along the US-Mexico border. This knowledge will help us design prevention interventions and impact the health along the Arizona-Sonoran border in ways that are responsive to adolescents.

General Results: Describe the general results of the project, including whether the planned results were achieved as expected, whether they were not, and the corresponding reasons. What were the project major accomplishments and why are significant in the context of your project

The final sample (n= 42) includes 29 students in Nogales, Sonora and 13 students in Nogales, Arizona. Nearly 55% of participants identified as female and the rest (45%) as males. Over half of the participants were under 18-years old (57%) and a similar percentage was enrolled in 12th grade. Forty percent of the participants were native to Nogales, Sonora or Nogales, Arizona and 12% were international migrants residing in Arizona. The rest of the adolescents resided in Nogales, Sonora including: 21% returnee students, 17% internal migrants, and 9.5% transborder students. Table 1 presents the sociodemographic characteristics and migratory status of study participants.

Characteristics	Sonora n(%)	Arizona n(%)	Both Nogales n(%)
Sex			
Female	15 (51.7)	8 (61.5)	23 (54.8)
Males	14 (48.3)	5 (38.5)	19 (45.2)
Age			
15-17 years	17 (58.6)	7 (53.8)	24 (57.1)
18-19 years	12 (41.4)	6 (46.2)	18 (42.9)
Grade			
10 th	3 (10.3)	1 (7.7)	4 (9.5)
11 th	9 (31.0)	5 (38.5)	14 (33.3)
12 th	17 (58.6)	7 (53.8)	24 (57.1)
Name of schools			
Conalep	5 (17.2)	0	5 (11.9)
Preparatoria Municipal La Mesa	2 (6.9)	0	2 (4.8)
Preparatoria Municipal El Rastro	1 (3.4)	0	1 (2.4)
Cetis 128	11 (37.9)	0	11 (26.2)
Cobach 1	4 (13.8)	0	4 (9.5)
Cobach 2	2 (6.9)	0	2 (4.8)
Lourdes Catholic School	4 (13.8)	3 (23.1)	7 (16.7)
Nogales High School	0	10 (76.9)	10 (23.8)
Student's migratory status			
Natives	9 (31.0)	8 (61.5)	17 (40.4)
Internal migrants	7 (24.1)	0	7 (16.7)
Returnees	9 (31.0)	0	9 (21.4)
International migrants	0	5 (38.5)	5 (11.9)
Transborder	4 (13.8)	0	4 (9.5)
Time of living in Nogales			
≤ 9 years	8 (27.6)	3 (23.1)	11 (26.2)
10-14 years	4 (13.8)	5 (38.5)	9 (21.4)
≥15 years	17 (58.6)	5 (38.5)	22 (52.4)
Data collection type			
Interview	13 (44.8)	5 (38.5)	18 (42.9)
Focus group	16 (55.2)	8 (61.5)	24 (57.1)

Our preliminary data analysis revealed themes emerging from the six distinct cohorts of high school adolescents along the Arizona-Sonora border: (1) native born adolescents in Nogales, Sonora; (2) native born adolescents in Nogales, Arizona; (3) internal Mexican migrant adolescents in Nogales, Sonora; (4) international Mexican migrant adolescents in Nogales, Arizona; (5) recent returnees residing in Nogales, Sonora; and (6) transborder adolescents in Nogales, Sonora who cross the border daily to go to school. While additional data analysis will be conducted, the two common themes emerging across all six groups are *place* (Nogales, Mexico, frontera, school) and *people* (family, adolescents, community). However, the recent returnees appear to have a different experience than the other groups of adolescents. The participants discussed having a lack of friends, experiencing bullying, and feeling culture shock when they first arrived in Nogales, Sonora from the US. They worried that the transition from an educational system in a country with many resources to a country with limited resources could affect their academic education. The feelings of invisibility and linguistic challenges are articulated by a focus group participant:

“...pues llegue y no sabía hablar bien el español, no sabía leer y ... faltaban como 3 meses para que se acabara el curso y la maestra no me prestó atención de enseñarme a leer ni nada. [*“... I arrived and could not speak Spanish well, I could not read and ... it was about 3 months before the school year ended and the teacher did not pay attention to teach me to read or anything else.”*] (estudiante del sexo masculino, *male student*)

Challenges: Discuss how you addressed both anticipated and unanticipated challenges in the course of the project. Please explain any delays or complications that occurred during the process of implementing your plans for this proposal. Is there anything that PTC could have done to assist you with addressing these challenges?

We encountered two primary challenges: participant recruitment and administrative delays. We anticipated some participant recruitment challenges due to the sensitive nature of our research question and unique participant characteristics. To navigate this challenge, we developed a recruitment plan targeting selected schools and student demographics by school. This plan ensured we recruited participants representing diverse perspectives. We also identified schools that we felt would provide support for our research project. Yet, in Sonora, Nogales, IRB safety concerns prevented us from conducting focus groups and interviews with adolescents outside of school hours; thus, we worked within those parameters to conduct all fieldwork. An unanticipated challenge was the difficulty in identifying and recruiting returnee students. We had to adjust our recruitment plan to identify these students from other sites. We also excluded one of the original schools Nogales, Sonora, from data collection due to the danger the neighborhood posed to the facilitators. Lastly, administrative delays in the ASU financial system led to delays in data collection, and one of our facilitators was unable to continue with the project due to work-scheduling conflicts. To address these concerns, we maintained close communication with the rest of the team, and we adjusted our data collection/transcription timelines as needed. Our challenges seem to be project specific, and we do not feel that PTC could have assisted us to ease these challenges.

External Funding: Tell where you are planning in applying for external funding. What external funding agencies are you targeting? Where are you in the funding development stage of your project?

We have received three additional grants related to the work on this project. First, we were awarded an ASU Watts College Internal Matching grant (\$13,000) to expand our PTC data collection in order to add non-migrants in Nogales, Sonora to the sample and to assist in offsetting GCAHR's in-kind cost-share contributions, enabling the study team to dedicate sufficient time and resources to the project. We have also been awarded funding (\$9,000) from the 2019-2020 PTC Research Seed Grant for our project, "Understanding the Social and Educational Needs of Returned Migrant Children in Nogales, Sonora." Our third grant proposal, "Dissemination of an efficacious youth prevention program in Mexico: scalability and sustainability," received funding (\$84,954) from the Global Consortium for Sustainability Outcomes (GCSO). This grant is in collaboration with El Colegio de la Frontera Norte (COLEF) and Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM). We are also submitting to the MacArthur Foundation 100&Change grant on August 5, 2019. This \$100 million grant proposal will seek to strengthen communities and adolescents in vulnerable social and cultural contexts.

General Budget/Grant Administration Issues: Describe the general progress of meeting budget expectations, including whether the funding helped your project to progress as planned. Briefly describe your experience in working with the staff who administered the award. Please include benefits and challenges in regards to the grant administration. What suggestions do you have for making this experience more efficient and beneficial for future researchers who are awarded a PTC grant?

Overall, the funding helped us progress as planned. This funding allowed us to hire interviewers and facilitators and to give adolescents incentives for participating in the study. The primary administrative challenge was delays in the ASU financial system for processing payments. It was extremely challenging to pay our staff (i.e., interviewers and transcribers) and obtaining incentives (i.e., participant gift cards) in a timely manner. This ultimately delayed the overall timeline of the project. We would recommend transferring the money directly to the institution in Mexico to ease these financial delays at ASU.

Overall grant experience: Briefly provide any recommendations for PTC in regards to the research cluster and individual research grants.

The PTC grant and resources were extremely valuable as it increased the opportunity for collaboration between Mexican and ASU researchers. This project allowed us to explore the complex social dynamics in the Sonora-Arizona border and how these affect adolescents. An important output of the PTC-funded project was the Arizona-Sonora Colloquium held April 4-5, 2019. This meeting allowed us to identify related issues, challenges, and resources of other PTC grant recipients. This led to the development of a virtual PTC seminar. The 17 participants included faculty, research assistants, and students from Mexican and U.S. universities. For the development of the virtual seminar, a platform was created at El Colegio de la Frontera Norte. Each week, a PTC fellow would present his/her research project, the progress in meeting the aims of the grant, and

the challenges of conducting research in the Sonora-Arizona region. The institutions participating in the PTC Virtual Seminar were Arizona State University (ASU), El Colegio de la Frontera Norte (El Colef), El Colegio de Sonora (El Colson), la Universidad de Sonora (Unison) y el Centro de Investigación en Alimentación y Desarrollo, A.C. (CIAD). Creating a supportive cadre of current PTC grant recipients was tremendously helpful. Our recommendation would be to formalize this process earlier in the grant cycle.

Annex II Calendario de presentaciones Programa de las Comunidades Transfronterizas Reunión virtual 10:00 a.m. -12:00 p.m.	
26 de abril	Impact of Anti-immigrant Sentiments on Adolescent Wellbeing in the Arizona-Sonora Border Region Arizona State University & El Colegio de la Frontera Norte
3 de mayo	Effect of the Immigration Process on Lifestyle Environmental and Biological Factors that Influence Chronic Disease Risk among Mexican Women in the Arizona-Sonora Border Arizona State University & Centro de Investigación en Alimentación y Desarrollo
20 de mayo	Beyond Children Migrants' Immigration Proceedings: Institutional Practices and Impacts on Asylum-Seeking Youth Arizona State University & El Colegio de Sonora
24 de mayo	Access to Justice by Undocumented Migrants Processed by the U.S. Court System Arizona State University & Universidad de Sonora